

agr! BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s Build our SFSC”

Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: Technological Corporation of Andalusia (CTA)

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“Let’s Build our SFSC!” Event Validation Report – Spain

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of the **Technological Corporation of Andalusia (CTA)** for the organisation and validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event in **Andalusia, Spain** organised on **March 29th, 2023**. This event is an online brokerage and networking event, to bring stakeholders of the local agri-food sector to present their products, meet others and negotiate partnerships based on the concept of Short Food Supply Chains. The event was organised using the Brella matchmaking platform that was selected as the most appropriate for the needs of the agroBRIDGES consortium, based on market research and negotiations with the sales departments of various candidate providers, in the frame of task 3.4.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s build our SFSC!” tool and measure its impact to the agrifood sector at local level. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** – Introducing the event report.
- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation, and implementation of the **Let’s build our SFSCs** event in **Andalusia, Spain**.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s build our SFSC” event organisation details

2.1 Event programme / agenda

The event took place on Wednesday, 29th of March of 2023. It was carried out to bring together producers and distributors from the agri-food sector in Andalusia. Different presentations and activities were developed which are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Topic / Short description	Date & Time (local)	Speakers	Location
Welcome and introduction to the Brella platform	General aspects and presentation of agroBRIDGES project.	11:00 – 11:30	Sofía Sánchez Seda (CTA Communication Technician)	Central stage
Andalusia Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs)	Explanation of SFSCs and presentation of success cases.	11:30 – 12:00	María Jiménez Portaz (CTA Innovation Consultant)	Central stage
Presentations by the participants	Get to know them, what are they doing and what do they expecting.	12:00 – 12:30	Assistants	Central stage
agroBRIDGES Toolbox	Introduction, description, and explanation of the different Toolbox.	12:30 – 13:00	Paula Rosa Álvarez (CTA Innovation Consultant)	Central stage
Conclusion	Contact information, let us keep in touch and work together.	13:00 – 13:10	María Jiménez Portaz (CTA Innovation Consultant)	Central stage
Bilateral meetings	Private meetings between assistants.	13:10 – 14:00	Assistants	Meeting rooms

2.2 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

For the organization of the event, within CTA, four people have participated in the organization. On the one hand, one of them have focused on communication: dissemination on social networks (LinkedIn, Twitter, website, writing an article, emails). Other three persons have been mainly in charge of contact with the invited people, they have designed the event programme, coordinating all the activities, etc. Two innovation consultants and one communications technician have been on charge of the presentations made, and the interactions with the participants, as well as, working on the Brella platform to learn how it works and to optimise all the possibilities it offers.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Communication Technician	1	Development of the promotional material, presence at the event, diffusion on social networks and emails.	In-house	2
Innovation Consultant	3	Development of the agenda and presentations, contact with invited people, dissemination and emails	In-house	2.5
Technical Responsible	1	Contact with invited people, dissemination and emails	In-house	1

2.3 Event material

The material used to promote the event is shown and described below. Templates developed by the agroBRIDGES project have been used for dissemination on social networks such as LinkedIn and Twitter (Figure 1). News of the event was included in the CTA Newsletter, which is sent to more than 6600 people weekly (Figure 5). In addition to the material for dissemination on social networks, personal and massive emails have been sent.

In addition, to facilitate access and use of the platform, a detailed Brella manual was created, with all the steps to follow for registration, participation, request, and acceptance of B2B meetings, among other information of interest (Figure 2). Figures 3 and 4 show the registration form that was disseminated, following the instructions of the work package leader.

Figure 1. Event invitation

CTA **agroBRIDGES**

¡Únete al evento online!

Miércoles, 29.03.2023
11:00 h – 14:00 h
en la Plataforma Brella

‘Construyamos nuestros Canales Cortos de Comercialización Alimentaria’
Evento de networking y cooperación entre empresas agroalimentarias, productores y HORECA de España

¡Regístrate!

Figure 2. User Manual of the Brella Platform

CTA **agroBRIDGES**

MANUAL USUARIO PLATAFORMA BRELLA

Networking online: ‘Construyamos nuestros Canales Cortos de Comercialización Alimentaria’

29-03-2023
11.00 H -14.00 H

Evento organizado por CTA en el marco del proyecto europeo agroBRIDGES: <https://www.agrobridges.eu/>

Figure 3. Registration form

CTA Acelera tu innovación

QUIÉNES SOMOS SERVICIOS ÁREA INTERNACIONAL CTA CLÚSTER AGENDA SALA PRENSA

Calendario de eventos y convocatorias

Regístrate ahora:

Nombre*

Apellidos*

Género*

Mujer

Hombre

Otro

Prefero no decirlo

Email*

Nombre de la organización*

Seleccione la descripción que más se ajuste a usted o a su organización*

Agricultores y/u otros productores

Proveedores de tecnología

Clústers, hubs y otras organizaciones de apoyo a empresas agroalimentarias

Asociaciones de productores

Asociaciones de consumidores

Otros

Quiero presentar mi negocio durante el evento*

Sí

No

Descripción de la empresa*

Figure 4. Registration form (continuation)

Descripción de los productos

Dirección de la empresa*

Email de la empresa

Teléfono de la empresa*

Facebook de la empresa

LinkedIn de la empresa

Web de la empresa

Confirmando que he leído la Política de Privacidad del proyecto agroBRIDGES y acepto el tratamiento de mis datos*

Sí

Consiento el tratamiento de mis datos para mi participación en futuras actividades de agroBRIDGES*

Sí

No

Acepto recibir newsletters y mensajes sobre las actividades de agroBRIDGES*

Sí

No

Todos los campos marcados con un asterisco (*) son obligatorios.

Enviar Limpiar formulario

Descargar datos

Por favor, lea atentamente la Política de Privacidad del proyecto agroBRIDGES y el Formulario de Consentimiento Informado que proporcionan información sobre el uso y protección de sus datos personales para este evento.

Figure 5. One of the CTA's newsletters with information about the event

2.4 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

2.4.1 Social Media Dissemination

We have created and shared 18 social media posts in our CTA's social media profiles in Spanish and English. The posts were showed to more than 6,700 followers of our Spanish Twitter account and more than 900 of our English one. Also, we have shared the event in our CTA's LinkedIn page, with more than 5,800 followers and in our personal LinkedIn profiles.

➤ Twitter posts

- 10/03/2023 <https://twitter.com/CTAndaluciaENG/status/1634147435080458240>
- 14/03/2023 <https://twitter.com/CTAndaluciaENG/status/1635574059990695938>
- 16-03-2023
<https://twitter.com/CTAndalucia/status/1636397306852573184?cxt=HHwWgIDUpcer07UtAAAA>
- 16-03-2023
<https://twitter.com/CTAndalucia/status/1636397306852573184?cxt=HHwWgIDUpcer07UtAAAA>

- 22-03-2023 <https://twitter.com/CTAndalucia/status/1638571598528630785?cxt=HHwWgsC-1f6LsL0tAAAA>
- 23-03-2023 <https://twitter.com/CTAndaluciaENG/status/1638922364388888576?cxt=HHwWgMC-Z Nz74tAAAA>
- 27-03-2023 <https://twitter.com/CTAndalucia/status/1640449875782279170?cxt=HHwWhICx3Y6ehsQtAAAA>
- 28-03-2023 <https://twitter.com/CTAndalucia/status/1640730800344760325?cxt=HHwWioC86Yn-hcUtAAAA>
- 28-03-2023 <https://twitter.com/CTAndaluciaENG/status/1640719202645602305?cxt=HHwWgsDTnYDbgMUTAAA>

➤ LinkedIn posts

- 13-03-2023 <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7041082112124329985/>
- 22-03-2023 <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7044296494211809281/>
- 23-03-2023 (LinkedIn María Jiménez) https://www.linkedin.com/posts/mariajimenezportaz_networking-construyamos-nuestros-canales-activity-7044315853730770947-hQcw?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- 23-03-2023 (LinkedIn Paula Rosa) https://www.linkedin.com/posts/paula-isabel-rosa-%C3%A1lvarez-241b0a175_ccca-agricultura-agroalimentaciaejn-activity-7043619132029775873-HFtN?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- 23-03-2023 (LinkedIn Sofía Sánchez) https://www.linkedin.com/posts/sofiasanchezseda_ccca-agricultura-agroalimentaciaejn-activity-7042177045690228737-Worg?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- 23-03-2023 (LinkedIn Nathalie Chavier) https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nathaliechavier_ccca-agricultura-agroalimentaciaejn-activity-7043873874832154628-fvPe?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- 25-03-2023 <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7045331987816943616/>
- 28-03-2023 https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ctandalucia_boletaednproyecta-activity-7046215825417981952-btzX?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

2.4.2 Newsletter Campaigns

To maximise the scope of the information, we designed a newsletters' campaign in Spanish language. Our CTA's corporate newsletters have more than 6,600 subscribers. We shared the information about the 'Let's build our SFSCs' in four campaigns during the month of March.

- 03-03-2023: <https://mailchi.mp/corporaciontecnologica/boletin-proyecta-actualidad-innovacion-1506045?e=3c7577875f>
- 10-03-2023: <https://mailchi.mp/corporaciontecnologica/boletin-proyecta-actualidad-innovacion-1506053?e=3c7577875f>
- 17-03-2023: <https://mailchi.mp/corporaciontecnologica/boletin-proyecta-actualidad-innovacion-1506077?e=3c7577875f>
- 24-03-2023: <https://mailchi.mp/corporaciontecnologica/boletin-proyecta-actualidad-innovacion-1506097?e=3c7577875f>

In addition, we sent a special newsletter to a special database with more than 70 contacts related with the agri-food sector:

20-03-2023 [https://mailchi.mp/corporaciontecnologica/workshop-demanda-de-soluciones-innovadoras-basadas-en-ia-y-robotica-en-elewit-plataforma-tecnologica-redeia-1506081?e=\[UNIQID\]](https://mailchi.mp/corporaciontecnologica/workshop-demanda-de-soluciones-innovadoras-basadas-en-ia-y-robotica-en-elewit-plataforma-tecnologica-redeia-1506081?e=[UNIQID])

2.4.3 Website Promotoinon

We included the information of the event and the inscription form in our website:

<https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/es/agenda/calendario-de-eventos-y-convocatorias/Networking-Construyamos-nuestros-Canales-Cortos-de-Comercializacion-Alimentaria/>

2.4.4 Stakeholders Dissemination

In order to reach new attendees for the event, we decided to involve different stakeholders in the dissemination of the agroBRIDGES event. To do so, we sent emails to our MAP in two different occasions, and we also sent a special newsletter to our agro events database (more than 70 subscribers).

In addition, we contacted with important stakeholders in Andalusia like associations of business, HORECA entities (CEA, Landaluz, Junta de Andalucía, HORECA, Universities...) and agrarian unions. Some of them shared the information in their social networks.

i.e. Publications of the Confederation of Employers of Andalusia (CEA):

<https://twitter.com/CEAes/status/1640640068200067073?s=20>

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7046406872337117185>

To increase the participation, we called by phone and sent personalised mails to public lists of distributors of ecological and bio products. The public list, with more than 80 business, is available here:

https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/export/drupaljda/DECO20_Listado_Puntos_de_venta_a_domicilio_2020_0817.pdf

2.4.5 Post-Event Dissemination

Once the event was finished, we decided to share it in our different channels.

First of all, we created a news item in Spanish and English in our website explaining the event (30-04-2023):

<https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/es/sala-de-prensa/comunicados/CTA-reune-a-productores-y-distribuidores-agroalimentarios-andaluces-en-una-jornada-de-networking-online/>

<https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/en/sala-de-prensa/comunicados/CTA-brings-together-Andalusian-agri-food-producers-and-distributors-at-an-online-networking-event/>

Secondly, we included the news item in our newsletter:

31-03-2023

<https://mailchi.mp/corporaciontecnologica/boletin-proyecta-actualidad-innovacion-1506117?e=3c7577875f>

Lastly, we shared this information in our social networks.

03-04-2023

https://twitter.com/CTAndalucia/status/1642826115919085569?cxt=HHwWgoC8sb_pvswtAAAA

03-04-2023 <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7048600539894304768>

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

The event was led by the CTA Innovation Consultants, María Jiménez Portaz and Paula Rosa Álvarez; and the CTA Communication Technician, Sofía Sánchez Seda, and was carried out through the Brella platform. The event started with a presentation about what agroBRIDGES is, how to use the Brella platform and the event agenda and information.

Secondly, we presented the current situation of the Andalusian agricultural sector and the importance of building Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs). At the same time, we gave participants the opportunity to present their products and services. We designed a public presentations space for attendees, in order to facilitate their communication and the booking of subsequent private meetings.

In addition, we presented the **agroBRIDGES Toolbox** to facilitate its use and the incorporation of new actors to the SFSCs.

Finally, attendees arranged bilateral private meetings in search of new collaborations.

Figure 6. CTA Innovation Consultant, Paula Rosa, presenting the agroBRIDGES Toolbox

3.2 Event participation

The event was attended by various companies and organisations interested in learning more about this proximity business model and sharing their experiences with those present.

A total of 13 people participated out of 21 registered, 12 one-to-one meeting requests were submitted and 7 of them were agreed by both parties. Table 3 describes the audience type and number of participants.

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers and companies	6
Consumers	3
Public entity	1
Consortium members	3
Total	13

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event by participants

Due to the complexity of the event, the barriers, and difficulties in finding participants, and the low number of attendees, it was decided to carry out the questionnaire during the event, in a dynamic and participatory way, to ensure that we would get responses from the participants.

Question	Yes		No		Not sure	
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	6		2		1	
Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Did you find this event helpful to meet professionals and businesses you can collaborate with?	0	9	0	0	0	1
Do you think that this event helped you see Short Food Supply Chains as a promising business alternative?	0	5	0	2	0	3
Did you find the matching and booking of one-to-one meetings with other people useful to identify and negotiate collaborations?	0	3	0	2	0	5
Was the event useful in supporting you to find interesting opportunities to collaborate with other businesses for the development of Short Food Supply Chains?	0	6	0	1	0	3
Question	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer not to answer
Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	0	5	0	4	0	1
Please provide any comments you may have about this event	"The event was generally of interest, but preferably organised in a physically friendly way."					

4.1.2 Validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

Although the idea of the online networking event could be interesting for the agroBRIDGES project, we found that outside the project, it was not sufficiently attractive to the public.

Considering the high number of agri-food entities in Andalusia, and the dissemination we have done, we have not received special interest in the event. We had sometimes to explain what the event consisted of over the phone or make reminder calls to those registered to create a Brella profile. The number of participants was not as high as expected or desired, and the number of bilateral meetings was not as high as the number of participants. For this reason and for our region, we find that the event did not have special relevance.

As far as our organization is concerned, at CTA we have spent time and effort on advertising the event. During the celebration, we met some new companies that we have invited to join the MAP of the project. In addition, we have been able to gather the needs of the producers and participants of the SFSCs of Andalusia about this type of business model. We have also expanded our database of agricultural companies from different parts of our region.

Despite the above, unfortunately the event has not been relevant enough.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments? If not, please explain your thinking.

From CTA and after our experience, we have concluded that we would not repeat this event as it is currently planned. Due to the technical complications of the Brella platform, as well as the little interest received among the guests, we found that the basic idea of online networking for the agri-food sector is perhaps too advanced for the level of digitalization and resources that our target audience has.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

There are several factors and limitations why, according to our experience and the opinions collected during the phone calls and emails we have made to participants and stakeholders, this event has not been as successful as expected.

One is the target audience of agricultural producers themselves, as many are not digitally savvy enough to be interested in an online event. In addition, they sometimes do not have enough time or staff in their company, which makes it difficult for them to access these types of events. Another frequent comment we have come across is that, at least in Andalusia, after the pandemic, face-to-face events are missed. Networking is an activity that many farmers are not used to and, if they do participate, they prefer to do it in a face-to-face format to get to know the participants.

On our part and as organizers of the event, we have also encountered difficulties that we have tried to overcome. The Brella platform is new to us, so we had to participate in a learning process to know how to use it and how to organize the event. In addition, we had to create a PDF user manual to teach participants how to create their profile and arrange private meetings.

On the end-user side, the Brella platform is also unfamiliar. People do not find it attractive to invest time in creating their profile on the platform or having to read a manual for it. In addition, the fact that it is not translated into our language (Spanish), makes it difficult to understand certain functionalities. We found that the Brella platform it is not accessible, and the time and diffusion invested in the event have not meant a greater success.

We found that the event would have been more fruitful if it was held on a platform such as Zoom, Google Meets or Teams, that only requires the participant to log in. It could have been nice to do a 'pre-event', only with the partners of the agroBRIDGES project, to test the use of the Brella platform before launching it directly to the target audience.

5. Conclusions

Our impressions of the event are that the target audience we are targeting is not interested, for various reasons, in online networking. Based on our experience, we would like to extract some lessons for the future. One is that the organization of this event and its dissemination must be prepared with more time to achieve greater participation.

The second is that having the institutional support of certain public bodies would have been a great boost. In our region, having the support of the regional public entity dedicated to agriculture, would have meant greater dissemination and recognition of the event and the agroBRIDGES project by possible attendees.

Finally, we recommend for future events to have the help of influential people in the agricultural sector sharing the information among their contacts through videos on social networks, publications and different dissemination channels.